

Can Electronic Word-of-Mouth and E-Trust drive Repurchase Intentions in Online Shopping? A Moderated Mediation Approach.

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ABSTRACT

Smartphones have revolutionized social, cultural, and economic interactions. Similarly, the use of online platforms for buying goods and services has increased by manifold irrespective of type of product and price. The e-commerce platforms are adopting various strategies to attract new users and enhance the satisfaction level of their existing customers to stay ahead in the competition. Electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) is a major influence on consumer online purchase behaviour. This study intends to assess the influence of e-WOM credibility and e-trust between the relationship of customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions in online platforms. Here a moderated-mediation model was used to examine how e-WOM credibility moderates the relationship between e-satisfaction and repurchase intention in online shopping mediated through e-trust among online customers. Purposive sampling was used to yield 409 samples. An online survey using Google Forms collected primary data using a structured questionnaire. The primary predictor of E-satisfaction was delivery service quality, indicating that fast and correct delivery boosts online purchasing consumer contentment. This shows that e-satisfaction indirectly affects re-purchase intention through e-trust. This in-depth understanding will help online retailers in developing tailored tactics to improvise customer experience and loyalty...

Keywords: E-satisfaction, e-trust, e-WOM, repurchase intentions, Online shopping, PLS-SEM.

INTRODUCTION:

The wide accessible of internet has facilitate bring the business to online platforms. Most of retail businesses have moved from “Bricks and mortar” model to “click and mortar” model (Dennis et al., 2002). To ensure the sustained existence of retailers, it is essential to increase the shopping experiences and satisfaction of customers who are indulge in online shopping. Indian e-commerce merchants understand the need to deliver superior customer service in order to achieve increased consumer satisfaction in the face of fierce competition. Customers choose an online shop based on factors such as service quality and delivery method in addition to the services provided. Poor quality lowers a company's ability to compete. The introduction of smartphones has had a significant impact on modern life, completely altering how individuals operate in social, cultural, and economic circumstances. The widespread availability of inventive and varied programs on cell phones has effectively transformed consumer behaviour, encompassing their shopping habits. The days of making conventional market visits are a thing of the past; these days, people can easily shop online with a simple swipe of their smartphone screen while lounging in their homes (Hasman et al., 2019). The online retail industry in India is projected to reach 200 billion USD in 2026. As per the statistics, the count of online buyer has been increased by 125 million

in India during the last three consecutive years, and again it has been predicted that 80 million new are going to be added by 2025 (E-Commerce Surge, 2023). By the year 2030, it is projected that the Indian e-commerce market will reach a global value of \$300 billion, indicating considerable growth (*Indian E-Commerce Industry Analysis*, 2024).

A strategy focused on offering superior customer service is crucial for success in a cutthroat online marketplace (Rita et al., 2019). Further, customer satisfaction was found to have a strong impact on afterwards behaviours consumers, such as repeat purchases, it is imperative for online firms to ensure it is successful. The modern perspectives of online retail highlight the significance of website quality in building consumer loyalty and satisfaction (J. E. Collier & Bienstock, 2006; Parasuraman et al., 2005). It was found that trust is significant when consumer feels lack of information, opportunist worries, and ambiguity (Pavlou et al., 2007). This also stands true when it comes to online purchase as well (J. Lee et al., 2011).

The recent studies from Greece examined the intercorrelation between e-service quality, user experience, and overall customer satisfaction (Mamakou et al., 2023). Jain et al. (2023) found a positive e-WOM intention is an outcome of e-service quality, e-WOM brand commitment and customer satisfaction in the online

shopping format. Considering the ongoing evolution of online buying, it is essential to examine the factors influencing customers' propensity to make repeat purchases online. However, there is limited evidence from research indicating that the repurchase intention of online customers is determined by e-satisfaction, which is then influenced by e-trust. The study has examined the relationship between electronic word of mouth (e-WOM), brand perceptions, and consumer purchase intentions in the Saudi hotel industry (Beyari & Garamoun, 2024; Sousa & Fortes, 2023). The current study investigates the role of e-WOM credibility and e-Trust in influencing the relationship between e-customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions in the setting of online shopping. Additionally, this study makes a unique effort to evaluate the moderating influence of electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) in enhancing the association between e-satisfaction and e-trust among online customers.

2 Review of Literature and hypotheses development

The online repurchase intention refers to customers' cognitive tendency to show involvement in future online transactions due to their positive perception and trust of a particular brand. Repurchase intention is defined by (Febriani & Ardani, 2021) as the deliberate cognitive process by which consumers choose to make repeat purchases in the future based on factors such as satisfaction and trust. Considering the ongoing evolution of online buying, it is essential to examine the factors influencing customers' propensity to make repeat purchases online. Numerous studies have looked at the connection between consumer satisfaction and propensity to make subsequent purchases. Hsu et al. (2006) found that customers' online purchasing behaviour is influenced by their level of satisfaction from online shopping. It was revealed that satisfaction with a website increases the likelihood of making additional purchases on the same online platform. Zhang et al. (2011) found a direct correlation between customer experiences and repurchase intentions. Ginting et al. (2023) found that in Indonesia, the repurchase intentions of e-commerce clients are primarily influenced by their satisfaction level, trust, e-WOM, and e-service quality. The elements have a significant impact on consumer loyalty and behavior in the e-commerce industry. The study highlights the importance of positive electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM), platform trust, customer satisfaction, and high-quality e-services in fostering customer loyalty and repurchase intentions.

2.1 E-service quality dimensions and e-satisfaction

E-service quality refers to the comprehensive assessments and opinions of customers on the excellence and standard of e-service provision in the online marketplace. The SERVQUAL model, created by (Parasuraman et al., 1985), has primarily been utilized in academic literature for the purpose of assessing and appraising service quality. Over the years, several measurements have been added to assess the quality of services, such as security

(Rita et al., 2019) and convenience (Eryiğit & Fan, 2021), along with customer privacy (Ma Sabiote et al., 2012), delivery services (X. Liu et al., 2008), return experience (Rintamäki et al., 2021), and website design (G. Lee & Lin, 2005). In order to achieve high-quality e-service in an e-commerce environment, it is crucial to prioritize satisfaction of customers (Ighomereho et al., 2022). Process quality and outcome quality of online shopping found to have a significant impact on satisfaction of online consumers (Collier & Bienstock, 2009). The level of satisfaction of online shoppers are influenced by online shopping attributes like product delivery, perceived security, information quality, and product variety (Anderson & Swaminathan, 2011; Mofokeng, 2021; Rita et al., 2019). Therefore, it is hypothesized that;

H1a: Customer Privacy has a positive effect on customer e-satisfaction.

H1b: Delivery Service has a positive effect on customer e-satisfaction.

H1c: Website Design has a positive effect on customer e-satisfaction.

H1d: Reliability has a positive effect on customer e-satisfaction.

H1e: Return experience has a positive effect on customer e-satisfaction.

2.2 E-satisfaction and e-trust in online shopping websites

Kim et al. (2009) defined e-satisfaction as the overall satisfaction experienced by customers following a purchase and repeated interactions with products or services on an online platform. More recent studies such as Martínez-Navalón et al. (2019), show how in tourism companies, user satisfaction on social networks influences trust in these companies. Lai (2014) demonstrated the relationship between satisfaction with a travel agency and improved trust in the travel agency. Another study elaborated by (Liang et al., 2018), explores the relationship between satisfaction, trust and repurchase intention. Kim et al. (2009) conducted a study that found that e-trust and service quality are influential factors in e-satisfaction. Gelashvili et al. (2021) demonstrated that the satisfaction of users who make restaurant reservations via a mobile apps has a direct impact on trust in those restaurants. It was proposed that;

H2: e-satisfaction on online shopping websites has a positive impact on e-trust

2.3 E-trust and re-purchase intentions in online shopping websites

E-trust refers to the level of confidence consumers have in online transactions, encompassing their expectations and willingness to accept associated risks (Corritore et al., 2003). Eid (2011) examined beliefs about trust from both affective and cognitive perspectives. The buying and payment process, the company's website, privacy and security, order fulfillment and after-sales support, and the company's brand name and reputation all affect the trust

in online transactions. (Yoon, 2002). Liao et al. (2017) conducted a study that demonstrated the significance of e-trust in influencing e-loyalty through e-satisfaction. E-trust is influenced by security and privacy concerns, and it acts as a mediator between security/privacy and repurchase intention. E-trust in the B2C e-commerce market boosts customer confidence and loyalty, leading to repeat transactions. The level of trust in relationships significantly influences the commitment between buyers and sellers (Liu & Chang, 2017). Miao et al. (2022) found that e-trust plays a crucial role in influencing consumers repurchase behaviour in online shopping. Hence, given this understanding, the following hypothesis is proposed;

H3: E-trust on online shopping websites has a positive effect on re-purchase intentions.

2.4 E-satisfaction and repurchase intentions in online shopping websites

Evidences supports that repurchase intention is influenced customer satisfaction and information quality (Miao et al., 2022). Positive online purchasing experiences, characterized by effectiveness, fulfilment, privacy, and high-quality information, lead to higher satisfaction levels. This subsequently impacts customers' intention to make further purchases from the same store or online platforms. Companies that prioritize customer service are able to acquire and retain new customers (Quan et al., 2020). Satisfied customers become less price sensitivity and are inclined to overlook minor service faults (Rodríguez et al., 2020). Shin & Lee (2018) demonstrated a strong positive correlation between e-satisfaction of customers and the intention to make future purchases in their research on online fresh food shopping malls. Online fresh food shopping malls can enhance repurchase rates, customer loyalty, and business profitability by improving e-consumer satisfaction through prompt, precise, and secure delivery (Ma et al., 2022). According to Miao et al. (2022), the satisfaction and intention of customers to make repeat purchases in online business-to-consumer (B2C) e-commerce are influenced by factors such as quality, trust, perceived value, and previous online experience. The level of customer satisfaction in e-commerce has a substantial impact on the probability of customers engaging in repeat transactions in Indonesia. Customer satisfaction is crucial for retaining clients as satisfied customers tend to make more purchases (Ginting et al., 2023; Thuy & Ngoc Quang, 2022). According to this argument, the following is postulated:

H4: e-satisfaction on online shopping websites has a positive impact on re-purchase intention

2.5 E-trust as a mediator

There are evidences where e-trust has been used as mediating variable in the context of online shopping. Bulut & Karabulut (2018) highlighted the role of e-trust as a mediator between e-WOM characteristics and consumers repurchase behaviour, positively impacting

online repurchase intention. Whereas, Trivedi & Yadav (2020) made an attempt to explore the extent to which e-trust and e-satisfaction mediate the effect of vendor-specific attributes and customer intention to repurchase from the same online platform. A strong relationship exists between consumer trust and repurchase intention, which is influenced by customer satisfaction. Customers' purchase behaviour is influenced by their trust in the e-commerce platform, which is mediated by customer satisfaction. The results support previous research highlighting the importance of trust in influencing repurchase intentions in online purchasing contexts (Ginting et al., 2023). (Elliott & Speck, 2005) claims that all e-retailer must put their sincere effort to ensure trust, as it considered to be a significant determinant of shaping attitude of high involved shoppers in retail websites. The mediating role of trust between web service quality and customer loyalty was assessed in the B2C E-Commerce of Vietnam. In similar manner, this study made a novel attempt by using e-trust as a mediating variable between e-satisfaction and repurchase intention. Hence, it can be hypothesised that;

H5: E-trust mediates the relationship between e-satisfaction and repurchase intention in online shopping.

2.6 E-WOM credibility as moderator

Customers' views of the dependability, validity, and explanatory value of easily available e-WOM data are called "e-WOM credibility" (Daowd et al., 2021). E-WOM credibility is consumers' perception of e-retailer websites' claims, reviews, and recommendations in relation to real-world conditions (Mannan et al., 2019). E-WOM credibility is how much customers trust other customers' reviews of products, services, and online retailers. Customers' credibility opinions affect whether they accept e-WOM claims in e-commerce (Wu & Wang, 2011). E-commerce shoppers often base their purchases on e-WOM. Positive word-of-mouth (WOM) boosts e-customer pleasure, perceived value, and trust, increasing their likelihood of buying again. It influences e-commerce consumer behaviour and provides important information and recommendations. Marketers often use expert reviewers or offer incentives to boost product e-WOM (Shin et al., 2014). Shin & Lee (2018) argue that e-WOM's number and quality boost e-Trust, which influences customers' online shopping intentions. According to Miao et al. (2022), internet shoppers repurchase intentions are strongly influenced by word-of-mouth (WOM). Bulut & Karabulut (2018) studied the amount and quality of e-WOM affects consumers' trust in online retailers, which affects their chance of making additional purchases online. The moderating effect of word-of-mouth enhances the influence of hospital elements on the perceived value of medical travel (Lu et al., 2016). While the impact of word-of-mouth (WOM) on purchase intention and behaviour has been extensively studied in several marketing scenarios, there is a lack of research on the influence of WOM credibility in relation to repurchase intentions in online purchasing. Subsequently, the following hypotheses arise:

H6: Word-of-mouth (WOM) significantly moderates the relationship between e-satisfaction and e-trust in online shopping websites.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework

3 Materials and methods

The study has used quantitative approaches to validate the suggested model, which evaluate the direct and indirect impacts of e-customer satisfaction on repurchase intentions. The target population for this study includes consumers who have experienced online shopping. Given the extensive scope of the population, a purposive sampling method has been utilized to collect 409 samples. According to Hair et al. (J. F. Hair et al., 2010), a "10-times rule" was adopted for deciding sample size, which builds on the assumption that the sample size should be greater than 10 times the maximum number of inner or outer model links pointing at any latent variable in the model. Accordingly, the sample size required for the present study turned out to be 30 items x 10 = 300. A structured questionnaire was developed to collect primary data using Google forms to conduct the online survey. Data were collected through an online survey distributed via email and social media platforms. The survey used a structured questionnaires using Likert-scale questions (ranging from 1 – strongly disagree to 5 – strongly agree) to assess levels of agreement towards dimensions of e-service quality, e-customer satisfaction, e-WOM, e-Trust, and repurchase intentions. The data was analysed using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) in PLS-SEM 4.0, which allows for the assessment of complex relationships between observed and latent variables. SEM will be particularly useful to test the mediation effect of e-Trust and the moderation effect of e-WOM on the relationship between e-customer satisfaction and repurchase intentions.

3.1 Measures

Web site design was evaluated using a three-item scale from Lee and Lin (G. Lee & Lin, 2005). Similarly, responsiveness and reliability were each measured using three-item scales derived from (Ashiq & Hussain, 2023). Delivery service (X. Liu et al., 2008), E-satisfaction (Wolfinbarger & Gilly, 2003), E-trust (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), and Repurchase intention (Doney & Cannon, 1997) were all assessed using three-item scales respectively which were used in the study of Miao et al. (Miao et al., 2022) and Rita et al. (Rita et al., 2019). E-WOM credibility was evaluated using a three-item scale from (Siddiqui et al., 2021). The return experience specific to online shopping was measured using a four-item scale from (Rintamäki et al., 2021). Lastly, a three-item scale was adapted from (Ma Sabote et al., 2012) was utilized to gauge customer privacy concerns. This multi-dimensional approach ensures a comprehensive assessment of key factors influencing online shopping behaviours.

3.2 Common method biasness (CMB)

The post-hoc procedure known as the Harman one-factor analysis is performed subsequent to data collection in order to ascertain whether the observed variance can be attributed to a single factor (Podsakoff et al., 2003). In this study, a Harman's single-factor test was conducted which produced a variance extraction of a single factor of 45.746%, which is less than 0.50 or 50%. Therefore, no CMV was detected.

4Data Analysis

Data analysis includes both descriptive statistics and SEM analysis. The frequency distribution table is used to present the sample profile. Whereas, the SEM model was

to establish the hypothetical relationship between the latent variables.

Table 1 Sample Profile

Variable	Categories	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	212	51.8
	Female	197	48.2
	Total	409	100.0
Age	Below 25	85	20.8
	25-35	155	37.9
	35-45	95	23.2
	45 and above	74	18.1
	Total	409	100
Education	Matriculation	85	20.8
	Under Graduation	112	27.4
	Graduation	143	35.0
	Post Graduation and above	69	16.9
	Total	409	100.0
Marital Status	Married	226	55.3
	Unmarried	183	44.7
	Total	409	100.0
Occupation	Student	143	35.0
	Service	124	30.3
	Business	76	18.6
	Housewife	45	11.0
	Retired	21	5.1
	Total	409	100.0

It can be viewed from the table 1 that among the 409 respondents, Male constitutes the significant proportion of (51.8%) and the female represent (48.2%). Out of 409 respondents, most of the respondents 35.0% have completed their Graduation followed by 27.4% are under graduates, 20.8% have completed their matriculation and only 16.9 % of respondents are having an educational qualification ever post-graduation or above. Regarding occupation it can be observed that majority of respondents were students (35.0%) then service holder (30.0%), followed by Businessman (18.6%) and housewives (11.0%). Majority of the respondents belongs to the age group of 25-35 years (37.9%) indicating younger respondents.

4.1 Measurement Model

This analysis assesses the reliability of constructs, the significance of factor loadings, convergence, and discriminant validity. The findings are presented in Table 2. According to the recommendation by (J. F. Hair et al., 2010), to achieve an acceptable level of convergent validity, the factor loadings should be more than 0.5. One item RE3, was excluded from the model because its factor loading was less than 0.5 (J. F. Hair et al., 2010). According to (George & Mallery, 1999), internal reliability was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha.

Table 2 Assessment of measurement model

Constructs	Items	Loadings	Alpha	C.R.	A.V. E	VIF
Reliability	REL1	0.811	0.796	0.879	0.709	2.688
	REL2	0.844				
	REL3	0.871				
Customer Privacy	CP1	0.850	0.801	0.881	0.713	2.461
	CP2	0.835				
	CP3	0.848				
Delivery Service	DS1	0.873	0.807	0.886	0.722	4.184
	DS2	0.819				
	DS3	0.857				
E-satisfaction	ESAT1	0.908	0.938	0.961	0.891	2.188
	ESAT2	0.962				
	ESAT3	0.960				
e-trust	ETRT1	0.967	0.941	0.962	0.894	2.188
	ETRT2	0.927				
	ETRT3	0.942				
e-WOM credibility	EWOM1	0.762	0.72	0.842	0.641	1.580
	EWOM2	0.852				
	EWOM3	0.785				
Return experience	RE1	0.886	0.82	0.884	0.667	2.278
	RE2	0.920				
	RE4	0.892				
Re-purchase intention in Online-shopping	RINT1	0.937	0.9	0.937	0.832	
	RINT2	0.860				
	RINT3	0.937				
Website Design	WD1	0.765	0.852	0.912	0.776	2.136
	WD2	0.931				
	WD3	0.936				

A value of Cronbach's alpha greater than 0.7 is considered acceptable. All items or constructs in the study satisfied the reliability criteria since their computed value exceeded 0.7. According to (Hair Jr. & Lukas, 2014) and (J. F. Hair et al., 2020), an internal composite reliability value greater than 0.7 indicates internal consistency and a convergent validity value greater than 5.0 is considered acceptable. In this study, the convergent validity value for

each construct exceeds the acceptable range. Further, multicollinearity was assessed by the variance inflation factor (VIF), and the VIF values of each construct are less than 5, providing evidence that the multicollinearity problem does not exist (see Table 2).

According to (Fornell & Larcker, 1981), it was ensured that the correlation between groups of constructs wasn't greater than the diagonal values, which are supposed to be the square root of the average variance retrieved for each

construct. Therefore, we confirm the discriminant validity and present the results in Table 3.

Table 3 Discriminant Validity

Constructs	RIL	CP	DS	ESAT	RPI	RE	WD	EWC	ET
RIL	0.842								
CP	0.608	0.844							
DS	0.741	0.736	0.85						
ESAT	0.651	0.71	0.841	0.944					
RPI	0.539	0.633	0.716	0.821	0.912				
RE	0.556	0.648	0.731	0.772	0.799	0.816			
WD	0.298	0.56	0.656	0.617	0.567	0.51	0.881		
EWC	0.434	0.534	0.659	0.604	0.591	0.59	0.513	0.801	
ET	0.63	0.686	0.684	0.737	0.731	0.743	0.429	0.623	0.946

Note: CP=Customer Privacy, DS=Delivery Service, ESAT=E-satisfaction, RPI= Re-purchase intention in Online-shopping, RIL=Reliability, RE=Return experience, WD=Website Design, EWC=e-WOM credibility, ET=e-trust

4.2 Structural Model and testing of hypothesis

Furthermore, a bootstrapping method involving 5,000 resamples was used to compute beta coefficients, t-values, and p-values (J. Hair et al., 2017). Table 4 and image 2 demonstrate that all the e-service quality dimensions (i.e. Delivery Services, website Design, Reliability and Return experience) were found to have a positive a significant impact on E-customer satisfaction in online shopping platforms. Hence, we support H1b, H1c, H1d, H1e, and H1f. Whereas, customer privacy is the only dimension of e-service quality was found to be insignificant ($\beta = 0.095$ and $p > 0.05$) and hence, H1a “Customer Privacy positively influences customers e-satisfaction in online shopping” was not supported.

Subsequently, it has been found that the impact of e-customer satisfaction on e-trust is both positive and significant ($\beta = 0.671$ and $p < 0.05$), thus, hypotheses H2 “Customer e-satisfaction has a positive effect on customer e-trust in online shopping” was supported. Proceeding further we evident a positive and significant influence of customer E-satisfaction on repurchase intention ($\beta = 0.618$ and $p < 0.05$) and we support H3 “E-satisfaction has a positive effect on customer repurchase intention in online shopping”. The mediator i.e. e-trust seems to have a positive impact on re-purchase intentions in online shopping platform ($\beta = 0.275$ and $p < 0.05$) and H4 “Customers e-trust positively influences customer re-purchase intentions in online shopping” was supported as well.

Figure 2 SEM model

Table 4 Path and Hypotheses Analysis

Paths	Beta	T-stat	P values	Alternative Hypothesis
Customer Privacy -> E-satisfaction	0.095	1.951	0.051	H1a Not Supported
Delivery Service -> E-satisfaction	0.409	6.796	0.000	H1b Supported
Website Design -> E-satisfaction	0.114	4.129	0.000	H1c Supported
Reliability -> E-satisfaction	0.086	2.114	0.035	H1d Supported
Return experience -> E-satisfaction	0.305	8.208	0.000	H1e Supported
E-satisfaction -> e-trust	0.671	14.428	0.000	H2 Supported
E-satisfaction -> Re-purchase intention in Online-shopping	0.618	13.379	0.000	H3 Supported
e-trust -> Re-purchase intention in Online-shopping	0.275	5.618	0.000	H4 Supported
Mediation effect (Indirect Effect)				
E-satisfaction -> e-trust -> Re-purchase intention in Online-shopping	0.185	5.969	0.000	H5 Supported
Moderation Effect				
e-WOM credibility x E-satisfaction -> e-trust	0.223	5.847	0.000	H6 Supported

This finding indicates the significant indirect impact of e-satisfaction on re-purchase intention through e-trust. The coefficient of 0.185 signifies a positive indirect correlation ($p < 0.05$), thus, we accept the H5 “Customer e-trust positively mediates the relationship between the customer e-satisfaction and repurchase intentions in online shopping”. This indicates that higher levels of e-satisfaction result in increased e-trust, which subsequently has a favourable impact on the desire to re-purchase from the online platform. This emphasizes the significance of establishing trust by ensuring customer pleasure as a primary catalyst for consumer loyalty and recurrent purchasing behaviour in online retail settings. The Variance Accounted for (VAF) is the indirect effect's Beta Coefficient divided by the total effect. According to Hair et al. (J. F. Hair et al., 2011), a VAF value below 20% indicates no mediation, a value between 20% and 80% indicates partial mediation, and a VAF value greater than 80% indicates full mediation. The value of VAF for the mediation of e-trust equals to 22.99 per cent that explains that e-trust partially mediates the relationship between e-satisfaction and repurchase intentions.

4.3 Moderation effect

This result indicates a significant moderation effect of e-WOM (electronic Word of Mouth) credibility on the relationship between e-satisfaction (electronic satisfaction) and e-trust (electronic trust). The positive coefficient ($\beta = 0.223$, $p < 0.000$) suggests that as the credibility of e-WOM increases, it strengthens the positive relationship between e-satisfaction and e-trust. Thus, we

accept H6. This implies that when customers find online reviews and recommendations to be credible, their satisfaction with the online service or product more effectively translates into trust in the online platform or seller.

Table 5 R² and Q² of endogenous constructs

Constructs	R²	Q²predict
E-satisfaction	0.773	0.766
Re-purchase intention in Online-shopping	0.708	0.63
e-trust	0.623	0.573

Results for endogenous constructs' R² (coefficient of determination) evaluations are presented in Table 5. Hair et al. (2014) states that values between 0.25 and 0.50 are weak, values between 0.50 and 0.75 are moderate, and values over 0.75 are substantial. Table 5 presents the results of the predictive relevance evaluation, Q². According to Hair et al. (2014), when the predictive relevance value is greater than 0, it means that the exogenous constructions are more powerful and relevant in terms of prediction than the endogenous ones.

5 Discussion

The strongest predictor of E-satisfaction was found to be the quality of delivery service which indicates that timely and accurate delivery significantly enhances customer satisfaction in online shopping environments. This finding corroborates prior studies which emphasize the importance of logistical efficiency and reliability in e-commerce settings (Pizzi et al., 2019). The return process also significantly impacts E-satisfaction in online shopping context. A smooth and customer-friendly return process can significantly enhance customer satisfaction, possibly by reducing perceived risk and increasing perceived reliability of the online merchant. Product return is more important in online retailing than offline retailing given that consumers often do not have the opportunity to see the product physically before purchase (Griffis et al., 2012). Similarly, responsiveness of customer service also plays a crucial role in enhancing E-satisfaction. This aligns with the service quality literature which highlights responsiveness as a critical determinant of customer satisfaction in service contexts (Ashiq & Hussain, 2023). A well-designed website contributes positively to E-satisfaction in online shopping, underscoring the importance of usability and aesthetic appeal in creating satisfying online shopping experiences (G. Lee & Lin, 2005).

In the same context, reliability of the online service providers is found to be an important determinant in maximising satisfaction level of online consumers, indicates that consistent performance by the e-commerce platform is appreciated by customers (Ashiq & Hussain, 2023) Surprisingly, the influence of customer privacy on E-satisfaction was not significant which can be inferred as privacy concerns are either not sufficiently addressed by online vendors. Then the e-commerce platforms need to use strong encryption standards (such as AES-256) can protect customer data from unauthorized access. Further, they can implement robust authentication mechanisms such as two-factor authentication (2FA) to ensure that only authorized users can access their accounts. The systematic improvements in maximising customer privacy in the vulnerable digital world will ensure safe transactions, trust building and satisfaction. E-satisfaction directly affects e-trust among the online buyers indicating that satisfaction with prior purchase experiences significantly builds trust in the e-commerce platform. Furthermore, E-satisfaction directly influences repurchase intentions highlighting the critical role of satisfaction in cultivating customer loyalty (Thuy & Ngoc Quang, 2022). The positive mediation effect suggests that efforts to improve customer satisfaction should lead to higher levels of trust and, consequently, a higher likelihood of customers are more likely to make further purchases. The interaction between E-satisfaction and e-WOM credibility significantly influences e-trust which signifies that the credibility of electronic word-of-mouth amplifies the impact of E-satisfaction on trust. This implies that trustworthy online reviews and recommendations can enhance the trust-building effect of customer satisfaction.

6 Conclusion

The study emphasizes the pivotal role of e-satisfaction in shaping customer trust and loyalty in online shopping contexts. By meticulously addressing factors such as delivery service, return policies, responsiveness, website design, and reliability, online retailers can enhance satisfaction, thereby boosting customer retention and trust. However, the surprisingly insignificant impact of privacy concerns warrants further investigation, possibly exploring different dimensions of privacy or varying consumer perceptions across demographics. This comprehensive understanding aids online retailers in crafting targeted strategies that address these critical elements, enhancing overall customer experience and loyalty. The research findings unequivocally demonstrate that E-satisfaction plays a crucial role in the domain of online buying, directly influencing customer trust and repurchase intentions. The study also examined the relationship between E-satisfaction and e-WOM credibility. It found that trustworthy online reviews strengthen the impact of customer satisfaction on generating trust. This indicates that reliable electronic word-of-mouth (e-WOM) serves as a potent catalyst for client trust, which in turn has a significant impact on repeat purchase choices. Overall, E-satisfaction is a complex concept that is greatly affected by factors such as the quality of delivery, return procedures, response, and the supportive influence of trustworthy electronic word-of-mouth. These components combined create a reliable atmosphere, which in turn promotes customer loyalty and motivates customers to make repeat purchases in online purchasing scenarios. Businesses are advised to prioritize five crucial areas in order to improve customer happiness, which is undeniably connected to trust and subsequent purchasing decisions.

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